

WorldFAIR WP09 Biodiversity FIP01

Organization	GO FAIR
Created by	Joe Miller (jmiller@gbif.org)
Based on	FIP Wizard 3, 3.0.17 (gofair:fip-wizard-3:3.0.17)
Project Phase	Defining FAIR Implementation Profile
Project Tags	Type: FIP
Created at	15 May 2023

I. About

Questions

No questions

II. Declare your FAIR Implementation Community

Questions

1

Select your FAIR Implementation Community

WorldFAIR WP09 Biodiversity

GBIF - the Global Biodiversity Information Facility - is an international network and data infrastructure funded by the world's governments and aimed at providing anyone, anywhere, open access to data about all types of life on Earth.

<http://purl.org/np/RAmGrWU8VeFW4C832nbioVSWfsBsP1b6FDneaG4hdbyi8#wf-wp09-biodiversity>

2

Who is the Community Data Steward?

0000-0002-6590-599X

3

Specify the start date for the validity of the FIP

2022-08-08

4

Specify the end date for the validity of the FIP

2050-12-31

III. Declarations for Findability

Questions

1

Declaration F1 Metadata: What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

DOI | Digital Object Identifier

The digital object identifier (DOI) system originated in a joint initiative of three trade associations in the publishing industry (International Publishers Association; International Association of Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers; Association of American Publishers). The system was announced at the Frankfurt Book Fair 1997. The International DOI Foundation (IDF) was created to develop and manage the DOI system, also in 1997. The DOI system was adopted as International Standard ISO 26324 in 2012. The DOI system implements the Handle System and adds a number of new features. The DOI system provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type. The DOI system is designed to work over the Internet. A DOI name is permanently assigned to an object to provide a resolvable persistent network link to current information about that object, including where the object, or information about it, can be found on the Internet. While information about an object can change over time, its DOI name will not change. A DOI name can be resolved within the DOI system to values of one or more types of data relating to the object identified by that DOI name, such as a URL, an e-mail address, other identifiers and descriptive metadata. The DOI system enables the construction of automated services and transactions. Applications of the DOI system include but are not limited to managing information and documentation location and access; managing metadata; facilitating electronic transactions; persistent unique identification of any form of any data; and commercial and non-commercial transactions. The content of an object associated with a DOI name is described unambiguously by DOI metadata, based on a structured extensible data model that enables the object to be associated with metadata of any desired degree of precision and granularity to support description and services. The data model supports interoperability between DOI applications. The scope of the DOI system is not defined by reference to the type of content (format, etc.) of the referent, but by reference to

the functionalities it provides and the context of use. The DOI system provides, within networks of DOI applications, for unique identification, persistence, resolution, metadata and semantic interoperability.

http://purl.org/np/RAnAWGdel_1GGmDAqv-vZjby5XqbL2ZujNz1vgwK_6cRI#DOI

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

- ✓ GBIF uses DOIs in two distinct ways worth mentioning here: - DOI resolves to a Digital Object/package that includes structured metadata for the dataset and structured data files conforming to a schema. - GBIF assigns a DOI to search results when a user requests a download

1.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

UUID | Universally Unique Identifier

A UUID is a 128-bit label used for information in computer systems.

http://purl.org/np/RA5ikgqnKqn071dwzXFdiXlnM8hWZRdFKsQjC_e5YRkEw#UUID

1.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2

Declaration F1 Data: What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for datasets?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

DOI | Digital Object Identifier

The digital object identifier (DOI) system originated in a joint initiative of three trade associations in the publishing industry (International Publishers Association; International Association of Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers; Association of American Publishers). The system was announced at the Frankfurt Book Fair 1997. The International DOI Foundation (IDF) was created to develop and manage the DOI system, also in 1997. The DOI system was adopted as International Standard ISO 26324 in 2012. The DOI system implements the Handle System and adds a number of new features. The DOI system provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type. The DOI system is designed to work over the Internet. A DOI name is permanently assigned to an object to provide a resolvable persistent network link to current information about that object, including where the object, or information about it, can be found on the Internet. While information about an object can change over time, its DOI name will not change. A DOI name can be resolved within the DOI system to values of one or more types of data relating to the object identified by that DOI name, such as a URL, an e-mail address, other identifiers and descriptive metadata. The DOI system enables the construction of automated services and transactions. Applications of the DOI system include but are not limited to managing information and documentation location and access; managing metadata; facilitating electronic transactions; persistent unique identification of any form of any data; and commercial and non-commercial transactions. The content of an object associated with a DOI name is described

unambiguously by DOI metadata, based on a structured extensible data model that enables the object to be associated with metadata of any desired degree of precision and granularity to support description and services. The data model supports interoperability between DOI applications. The scope of the DOI system is not defined by reference to the type of content (format, etc.) of the referent, but by reference to the functionalities it provides and the context of use. The DOI system provides, within networks of DOI applications, for unique identification, persistence, resolution, metadata and semantic interoperability.

http://purl.org/np/RAnAWGdel_1GGmDAqv-vZjby5XqbL2ZujNz1vgwK_6cRI#DOI

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

- ✓ GBIF uses DOIs in two distinct ways worth mentioning here: - DOI resolves to a Digital Object/package that includes structured metadata for the dataset and structured data files conforming to a schema. - GBIF assigns a DOI to search results when a user requests a download

2.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

UUID | Universally Unique Identifier

A UUID is a 128-bit label used for information in computer systems.

http://purl.org/np/RA5ikgqnKqn071dwzXFdiXInM8hWZRdFKsQjC_e5YRkEw#UUID

2.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3

Declaration F2: What metadata schema do you use for findability?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DwC-A | Darwin Core Archive

DwC-A is a biodiversity informatics data standard that makes use of the Darwin Core terms to produce a single, self contained dataset for sharing species-level (taxonomic), species-occurrence data, and sampling-event data. An archive is a set of text files, in standard comma- or tab-delimited format, with a simple descriptor file (called meta.xml) to inform others how the files are organized.

http://purl.org/np/RAalb4yUuh8_oDKKVBfilFEmwUFORrAaxfx_XqvHazNfU#DwC-A

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

ABCD | Access to Biological Collection Data

The Access to Biological Collections Data (ABCD) Schema is a standard for the access to and exchange of data about primary biodiversity data. It is compatible with several existing data standards and supports several datasets.

<http://purl.org/np/RAezTbjDwWyvAHodv7FSJvF4d0sqG5H9bhK0QUMgq93R8#ABCD>

3.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DC | Dublin Core

The Dublin Metadata Element Set, which is often called Dublin Core (DC), is a standardized metadata scheme for description of any kind of resource such as documents in electronic and non-electronic form, digital materials (such as video, sound, images, etc) and composite media like web pages. Dublin Core Metadata may be used for multiple purposes, from simple resource description, to combining metadata vocabularies of different metadata standards, to providing interoperability for metadata vocabularies in the Linked Data cloud and Semantic Web implementations. Please note that this version of the specification for the Dublin Core Element Set 1.1 is somewhat out of date, although it is not officially deprecated. The DCMI Metadata Terms specification is linked to this record and is the current documentation that should be used for the Dublin Core Element Set 1.1.

http://purl.org/np/RApwFvegOdPfNuKIF64wctAzaffAv3j_2kAU9y6kfBoy8#DCMI

3.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

3.b.1.d.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DataCite Metadata Scheme

The DataCite Metadata Schema is a list of core metadata properties chosen for an accurate and consistent identification of a resource for citation and retrieval

http://purl.org/np/RAko0U2Q8boW-drM8t11DcbX6lxu2mcSQf-2BrM07geIQ#datacite_metadata_scheme

3.b.1.d.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.d.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3.b.1.e.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

**EML GBIF Profile Metadata | Ecological Metadata Language Global Biodiversity Information
Facility Profile Metadata**

The GBIF Metadata Profile is primarily based on the Ecological Metadata Language (EML)6 . The GBIF profile utilises a subset of EML and extends it to include additional requirements that are not accommodated in the EML specification.

http://purl.org/np/RA69xklqUA_c_76i3K-IsQ8RlxK-aF0jos6Gma_69PaIQ#EML_GBIF_Profile

3.b.1.e.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.e.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

3.b.1.f.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

EML | Ecological Metadata Language

The Ecological Metadata Language (EML) metadata standard was originally developed for the earth, environmental and ecological sciences. It is based on prior work done by the Ecological Society of America and associated efforts. It has been developed to document any research data, and as such can be used outside of these original subject areas. EML is implemented as a series of XML document types that can be used in a modular and extensible manner to document ecological data. Each EML module is designed to describe one logical part of the total metadata that should be included with any ecological dataset.

http://purl.org/np/RAUOTQKnMjCWdbbaEXfelgKYEK7CZQ2PhiHIM_gDrksdM#EML

3.b.1.f.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.f.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

3.b.1.g.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Schema.org Dataset

Metadata schema contained in a catalog

http://purl.org/np/RAfpqImxNsTJLDAV3ZvcQBoddyZf-YhI2WHXFpGHOLe-Y#Schema.org_Dataset

3.b.1.g.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.g.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

4

Declaration F3: What is the schema that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

4.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

4.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DataCite | DataCite Ontology

The DataCite Ontology (DataCite) is an ontology that enables the metadata properties of the DataCite

Metadata Schema Specification (i.e., a list of metadata properties for the accurate and consistent identification of a resource for citation and retrieval purposes) to be described in RDF.

http://purl.org/np/RANGw57Qlx5BklwMWCP1srqv4KG1o1I8cvA2IRaHq_HDg#DataCite

4.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

5

Declaration F4 Metadata: Which service do you use to publish your metadata records?

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

5.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

5.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DataCite | DataCite Ontology

The DataCite Ontology (DataCite) is an ontology that enables the metadata properties of the DataCite

Metadata Schema Specification (i.e., a list of metadata properties for the accurate and consistent identification of a resource for citation and retrieval purposes) to be described in RDF.

http://purl.org/np/RANGw57Qlx5BklwMWCP1srqv4KG1o1I8cvA2IRaHq_HDg#DataCite

5.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

5.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

GBIF search engine | Global Biodiversity Information Facility Search Engine

GBIF search engine provides free and open access to biodiversity data.

http://purl.org/np/RAANOJAdT5AYQIA5SMsTOGb6aHjhyhd8o2nkSqX1UeWDU#GBIF_search_engine

5.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

5.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Google Dataset Search

Google Dataset Search is a search engine from Google that helps researchers locate online data that is freely available for use.

http://purl.org/np/RAUhotKhSj2m1ftHGXPAYyL2QgY60L6mYrunOzQwGZJ44#Google_Dataset_Search

5.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

6

Declaration F4 Datasets: Which service do you use to publish your datasets?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

6.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

6.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DataCite | DataCite Ontology

The DataCite Ontology (DataCite) is an ontology that enables the metadata properties of the DataCite Metadata Schema Specification (i.e., a list of metadata properties for the accurate and consistent identification of a resource for citation and retrieval purposes) to be described in RDF.

http://purl.org/np/RANGw57Qlx5BklwMWCP1srqv4KG1o1I8cvA2IRaHq_HDg#DataCite

6.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

a. Currently in use by the community

6.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

6.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

GBIF search engine | Global Biodiversity Information Facility Search Engine

GBIF search engine provides free and open access to biodiversity data.

http://purl.org/np/RAANOJAdT5AYQIA5SMsTOGb6aHjhyhd8o2nkSqX1UeWDU#GBIF_search_engine

6.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

6.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

6.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Google Dataset Search

Google Dataset Search is a search engine from Google that helps researchers locate online data that is freely available for use.

http://purl.org/np/RAUhotKhSj2m1ftHGPXAYyL2QgY60L6mYrunOzQwGZJ44#Google_Dataset_Search

6.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

6.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

- ✓ Google Dataset Search indexes both described and downloaded datasets.

IV. Declarations for Accessibility

Questions

1

Declaration A1.1 Metadata: Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

REST | Representational state transfer

REST defines a set of constraints for how the architecture of an Internet-scale distributed hypermedia system, such as the Web, should behave.

<http://purl.org/np/RAszH6IU-Zc3UO7MHPKj1Lb0dmMmaTJrRvQ0jqpXMyFY4#REST>

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

1.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

OAI-PMH Schema | Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting Schema

The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting Schema (OAI-PMH Schema) provides a formal structure for validating responses as part of the OAI-PMH Protocol. The OAI-PMH Protocol is a low-barrier mechanism for repository interoperability. Data Providers are repositories that expose structured metadata via OAI-PMH. Service Providers then make OAI-PMH service requests to harvest that metadata. OAI-PMH is a set of six verbs or services that are invoked within HTTP.

http://purl.org/np/RAnwFn9lcKK8S2tccnwPZJw-0_hF5N03BL-8BuchPHtvQ#OAI-PMH

1.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

2

Declaration A1.1 Datasets: Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

REST | Representational state transfer

REST defines a set of constraints for how the architecture of an Internet-scale distributed hypermedia system, such as the Web, should behave.

<http://purl.org/np/RAszH6IU-Zc3UO7MHPKj1Lb0dmMmaTJrRvQ0jqpXMyFY4#REST>

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

 This question has not been answered yet!

2.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

OAI-PMH Schema | Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting Schema

The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting Schema (OAI-PMH Schema) provides a formal structure for validating responses as part of the OAI-PMH Protocol. The OAI-PMH Protocol is a low-barrier mechanism for repository interoperability. Data Providers are repositories that expose structured metadata via OAI-PMH. Service Providers then make OAI-PMH service requests to harvest that metadata. OAI-PMH is a set of six verbs or services that are invoked within HTTP.

http://purl.org/np/RAnwFn9lcKK8S2tccnwPZJw-0_hF5N03BL-8BuchPHtvQ#OAI-PMH

2.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ This question has not been answered yet!

3

Declaration A1.2 Metadata: Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for metadata records?

- a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

3.a.1

Considerations (optional)

✗ This question has not been answered yet!

4

Declaration A1.2 Datasets: Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for datasets?

✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

4.a.1

Considerations (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

5

Declaration A2: What metadata preservation policy do you use?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

5.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

5.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

RDA CTS | RDA Core Trust Seal Certification

The RDA Repository Audit and Certification DSA–WDS Partnership Working Group (WG) produced a two-part recommendation, one of which includes a Catalogue of Common Procedures for certification. The goal of the effort was to create a set of harmonized Common Procedures for certification of repositories at the basic level, drawing from the procedures already put in place by the Data Seal of Approval (DSA) and the ICSU World Data System (ICSU-WDS). These procedures are intended to support the implementation of the Catalogue of Common Requirements developed by the WG to harmonize the certification criteria previously established by the DSA and ICSU-WDS.

http://purl.org/np/RAOaajEdLrXIAiADDOPTbp5kwltGjsjS3nmWGnjEVSLTk#RDA_CTS

5.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

V. Declarations for Interoperability

Questions

1

Declaration I1 Metadata: What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?

- ✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

1.a.1

Considerations (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2

Declaration I1 Datasets: What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DwC-A | Darwin Core Archive

DwC-A is a biodiversity informatics data standard that makes use of the Darwin Core terms to produce a single, self contained dataset for sharing species-level (taxonomic), species-occurrence data, and sampling-event data. An archive is a set of text files, in standard comma- or tab-delimited format, with a simple descriptor file (called meta.xml) to inform others how the files are organized.

http://purl.org/np/RAalb4yUuh8_oDKKVBfilFEmwUFORrAaxfx_XqvHazNfU#DwC-A

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

2.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

JSON Schema | JavaScript Object Notation Schema

JSON Schema is a vocabulary that allows you to annotate and validate JSON documents.

http://purl.org/np/RAILCugRZltlBCt_KATatwxJrkdDfxC3EDbCHML172Bhl#JSON_Schema

2.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

3

Declaration I2 Metadata: What structured vocabulary do you use to annotate your metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

ISO 3166-1:2013 Codes for the representation of names of countries and their subdivisions - Part 1: Country codes

ISO 3166-1:2013 is intended for use in any application requiring the expression of current country names in coded form. It also includes basic guidelines for its implementation and maintenance.

http://purl.org/np/RAKy68K-ubbaV8BKrbYyJQ1NYKcCkvQPpgrQ7rdWbvjRU#ISO_3166

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

3.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DwC-A | Darwin Core Archive

DwC-A is a biodiversity informatics data standard that makes use of the Darwin Core terms to produce a single, self contained dataset for sharing species-level (taxonomic), species-occurrence data, and sampling-event data. An archive is a set of text files, in standard comma- or tab-delimited format, with a simple descriptor file (called meta.xml) to inform others how the files are organized.

http://purl.org/np/RAalb4yUuh8_oDKKVBfilFEmwUFORrAafx_XqvHazNfU#DwC-A

3.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✓ GBIF is currently expanding its use of community-curated controlled vocabularies within the framework of Darwin Core.

4

Declaration I2 Datasets: What structured vocabulary do you use to encode your datasets

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

4.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

4.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DwC-A | Darwin Core Archive

DwC-A is a biodiversity informatics data standard that makes use of the Darwin Core terms to produce a single, self contained dataset for sharing species-level (taxonomic), species-occurrence data, and sampling-event data. An archive is a set of text files, in standard comma- or tab-delimited format, with a simple descriptor file (called meta.xml) to inform others how the files are organized.

http://purl.org/np/RAalb4yUuh8_oDKKVBfilFEmwUFORrAaxfx_XqvHazNfU#DwC-A

4.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

GBIF is currently expanding its use of community-curated controlled vocabularies within the framework of Darwin Core.

5

Declaration I3 Metadata: What semantic model do you use for your metadata records?

b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

5.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

5.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DwC-A | Darwin Core Archive

DwC-A is a biodiversity informatics data standard that makes use of the Darwin Core terms to produce a single, self contained dataset for sharing species-level (taxonomic), species-occurrence data, and sampling-event data. An archive is a set of text files, in standard comma- or tab-delimited format, with a simple descriptor file (called meta.xml) to inform others how the files are organized.

http://purl.org/np/RAalb4yUuh8_oDKKVBfilFEmwUFORrAaxfx_XqvHazNfU#DwC-A

5.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

5.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

ABCD | Access to Biological Collection Data

The Access to Biological Collections Data (ABCD) Schema is a standard for the access to and exchange of data about primary biodiversity data. It is compatible with several existing data standards and supports several datasets.

<http://purl.org/np/RAezTbjDwWyvAHodv7FSJvF4d0sqG5H9bhK0QUMgq93R8#ABCD>

5.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

- This question has not been answered yet!*

5.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

EML GBIF Profile Metadata | Ecological Metadata Language Global Biodiversity Information

Facility Profile Metadata

The GBIF Metadata Profile is primarily based on the Ecological Metadata Language (EML)6 . The GBIF profile utilises a subset of EML and extends it to include additional requirements that are not accommodated in the EML specification.

http://purl.org/np/RA69xklqUA_c_76i3K-lsQ8RlxK-aF0jos6Gma_69PalQ#EML_GBIF_Profile

5.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

6

Declaration I3 Datasets: What semantic model do you use for your datasets?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

6.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

6.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

DwC-A | Darwin Core Archive

DwC-A is a biodiversity informatics data standard that makes use of the Darwin Core terms to produce a single, self contained dataset for sharing species-level (taxonomic), species-occurrence data, and sampling-event data. An archive is a set of text files, in standard comma- or tab-delimited format, with a simple descriptor file (called meta.xml) to inform others how the files are organized.

http://purl.org/np/RAalb4yUuh8_oDKKVBfilFEmwUFORrAaxfx_XqvHazNfU#DwC-A

6.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

6.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

VI. Declarations for Reusability

Questions

1

Declaration R1.1 Metadata: Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?

- ✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

1.a.1

Considerations (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2

Declaration R1.1 Datasets: Which usage license do you use for your datasets?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CC0 1.0 | CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication

You can copy, modify, distribute and perform the work, even for commercial purposes, all without asking permission.

<http://purl.org/np/RAq55jS4TCF-u0HLARDjWevzMv8k-NY7737bSJVzRAY2w#CC0-1.0>

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

2.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

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http://purl.org/np/RAQ_sGdY_Qc7I1O_zmn4nr-pMBOxKU04Ur9s998rS6Fc#CC-BY-4.0

2.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

2.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

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http://purl.org/np/RANw_e-9CEfADSpQKbEVn5G7qu_jczqdJUNssOzYXEvfA#CC-BY-NC-4.0

2.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3

Declaration R1.2 Metadata: What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

EML GBIF Profile Metadata | Ecological Metadata Language Global Biodiversity Information Facility Profile Metadata

The GBIF Metadata Profile is primarily based on the Ecological Metadata Language (EML)6 . The GBIF profile utilises a subset of EML and extends it to include additional requirements that are not accommodated in the EML specification.

http://purl.org/np/RA69xklqUA_c_76i3K-IsQ8RlxK-aF0jos6Gma_69PalQ#EML_GBIF_Profile

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

 This question has not been answered yet!

4

Declaration R1.2 Datasets: What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?

- a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

4.a.1

Considerations (optional)

 This question has not been answered yet!

5

Declaration R1.3: Your community uses this FAIR Implementation Profile to link to domain-relevant community standards. Please acknowledge this statement by clicking on 'Read and understood'.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

VII. Register a new resource as a nanopublication

Questions

No questions